

Role and Challenges of Women Entrepreneur

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Abstract

Based on the general concept of an entrepreneur, women entrepreneurs may be defined as the women or group of women who initiate, organize and operate a business enterprise. Women Entrepreneur refers to business or organization started by a women or group of women. There has been a change in role of women due to growth in education industrialization and awareness of democratic values. In that, so many challenges are faced by the women Entrepreneur are discussed in it. Today's world is changing at political and economic transformations seem to be occurring everywhere as countries convert from command to demand economies, dictatorships move toward democracy, and monarchies build new civil institutions. These changes have created economic opportunities for women who want to own and operate businesses. Today, women in advanced market economies own more than 25% of all businesses and women-owned businesses in Africa, Asia, Eastern Europe and Latin America are growing rapidly. This paper focuses on role and challenges of woman entrepreneur.

Keywords: Entrepreneur, Challenges, Role, Support etc.

Introduction

Entrepreneurship is the process in which women initiate a business, gather all resources undertake risks face challenges, provide employment to others and manages the business independently.

Role of Women Entrepreneur

Many successful businesses are run by women some of whom are very skilled in entrepreneurial activities. Women entrepreneurs in both developed and developing countries are socially powerful in terms of education and making a positive impact on the society. It is important to study how women in business and their skills can be utilized to achieve a sustainable economy in a developing nation. The survey has indicated how women entrepreneurs can be positioned to play an important role in promoting sustainable practices in the economy.

In most countries, regions and sectors, the majority of business owner/managers are male. The rates of self employment among women are increasing in several countries. But due to some troubles the women entrepreneurs cant able to achieve the success.

Role of Women Entrepreneur

Women entrepreneurs are less in number in India. The entrepreneurial skills of women were till recently limited to an extension of kitchen activities. Women entrepreneurs were popularly engaged in the 3 Ps, such as making and marketing of pickles, papads and powders (masalas). However, on account of the various schemes introduced for creating job opportunities and for encouraging women in business, these activities are now diversifying.

The Planning Commission, Central and State Government have realized that women should be in the main stream of economic development. The development of small-scale enterprises by women is seen as an appropriate way to attack poverty at the grass-root level. Such units employ women themselves and others who take up jobs in their units. This solves the unemployment problem and generates income in the economy. Under the poverty alleviation programme model in India, unemployed men and women are encouraged to generate income and break the poverty cycle.

Improvement in living standards: With the setting up of small scale industries, reduction of scarcity of essential commodities and introducing new products can be achieved. Women entrepreneurs in this country are producing variety of goods on a large scale and offering them at low rates, In Creativity At Creative Startups, we are driven to discover and invest in the best creative entrepreneurs, the founders building the creative giants of tomorrow. We keep in mind that with each accelerator we deliver, we are putting into orbit startups that might grow into behemoths. So we go the extra mile to make sure the entrepreneurs we accelerate represent a diverse swath of lifestyles, backgrounds, and communities.

Challenges of Women Entrepreneur

Lack of Family Support

In India, it is almost only a woman's duty to look after the children, other members of the family and also attend to all the household chores. Here the man plays a secondary or an insignificant role. Women's involvement in family problems drains them of energy and also leaves little time for them to participate in the economic activities.

Qualification

Women in India are discouraged to learn more than the male members of the family . There is also a widespread illiteracy problem among them . Sixty percent of the women are still illiterate in India. This illiteracy has become the root cause of a number of social and economic problems. Due to lack of education and that too a qualitative one, women are not aware of business , technology and market knowledge . Lack of education also results in lack of confidence, which in turn creates problems in setting and running business enterprises for women.

Financial Problems

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Conclusion

In the majority of women operate their enterprises under very adverse conditions. Not only in financial condition and also is it difficult for them to find premises, find markets for their products, access information and credit. But they also have limited access to training especially in the rural areas. Their educational levels are low, they are responsible for all the domestic chores and they are very much lack of family support to manage their timing for both family and enterprise, even if they do want to grow their enterprises. Women entrepreneurs are need to be which help identify higher potential business opportunities, develop markets for their products, improve product quality and marketing skills, good financial support and secure better site or establishment.

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